

THE SET OF ABILITIES THAT CHARACTERIZE THE “PEDAGOGICAL SKILL” OF A TEACHER

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Abstract. *The article focuses on the character of a teacher from pedagogical skill. The paper analyses pedagogy and set of abilities that can contain a range of characteristics.*

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Human abilities have enormous social and personal value. The ability provides adequate support to ensure high labor productivity, as a result, the rapid growth of social wealth in quantitative and qualitative terms, and the development of society. This article outlines scientific considerations about the need for future teachers to discover their intelligence and abilities and learn to use them in their place.

Ability is an individual psychological characteristic of a person; it means a set of individual mental qualities that express the ability to perform a certain activity and the subjective conditions for the successful performance of work.

Ability characterizes the individual capabilities of a teacher. Under the same conditions, capable teachers achieve greater success in their activities than less capable ones. Any complex innovative technologies, modern information and communication technologies, integrations, universal innovations in the field of science are first mastered by the teacher, and then, thanks to his knowledge, skills and abilities, they are conveyed to the consciousness and thinking of students. As you know, the requirements for a teacher's professional activity are increasing every year. This is the requirement of the present time. Therefore, the term “pedagogical skill” in relation to a teacher will never lose its status, but will be improved from year to year.

Let us give the following definitions of a teacher's “pedagogical skill”, given by our scientists and refined to this day:

a) Pedagogical skills - perfect mastery of professional knowledge, skills and abilities by the teacher;

b) Pedagogical skills – a set of professional qualities of a teacher that contribute to the successful implementation of teaching activities;

c) Pedagogical skill - the highest level of a teacher's pedagogical activity;

g) Pedagogical skills - the teacher's important attitude towards professionalism;

d) Pedagogical skills - mastering, choosing and using modern information technologies and innovative technological tools and teaching methods by the teacher in the educational process;

e) Pedagogical skills - rapid assimilation and modernization of integration and modernization, included in all branches of pedagogical and methodological knowledge and carrying out activities in accordance with them;

j) Pedagogical mastery is a process that ensures the management of a teacher's professional activity, supporting and regulating the pedagogical and psychological balance in education.

Yu.P. Azarov, V.I. Grabeklis, I.A. Zyazyun, N.V. Kuzmina, V.P. Simonov, V.A. Slastenin, V.A. Sukhomlinsky, G.I. Khozyainov, E. According to scientists such as N. Shiyanov, A. I. Sherbakov, the concept of "pedagogical skill" includes only the teacher's professional knowledge, abilities and skills. These comments cannot be evaluated as positive or negative, because the definitions given in relation to the concept of "pedagogical skill" are expressed at a level comparable to their time.

L.M. Mitina, listed above setting a past pedagogical goal, pedagogical thinking, pedagogical reflection, personal characteristics of the teacher, such as pedagogical etiquette and moral standards, and characteristics of pedagogical abilities included in the group.

According to A.K. Markova, "the setting of a pedagogical goal is the teacher's need for planning his work and at the same time the knowledge of the teacher based on the society and his personal goals ability to present to students.

In the studies of V.P. Simonov, the following set of abilities was proposed:

- the ability to promote problematic tasks;
- the ability to make a unique decision in pedagogical activity;
- the ability to foresee and predict the situation;
- the ability to manage oneself;
- able to communicate with students and the pedagogical team ability;
- to create creativity in various professional activities of the teacher the ability to create a delivery zone.

According to V.P. Galakhova, the perfect classification of "pedagogical skill" should be sought from the teacher's ability to use pedagogical techniques. She emphasizes that the pedagogical technique is "a set of abilities that allows the teacher to express himself more vividly, creatively, and deeply as a person, to achieve high results in professional activity, to convey his position, opinion, and knowledge to students by heart." Pedagogical technique includes the ability to control one's own behavior and the ability to influence a child's personality and a group of children.

When analyzing scientific pedagogical literature, a number of unclear limits of pedagogical skills are observed. In particular, Howard Gardner called abilities a set of intelligences and distinguished seven aspects of it. Scientist Olga Matveeva, who psychologically analyzed six of these aspects of intelligence, emphasizes their importance as a teacher's ability and describes them as follows:

1. Communication (communicative) ability: The teacher can create a positive mental climate in the classroom with students in the classroom and extracurricular processes.

2. The ability to foresee events: This type of ability is manifested in the vigilance of every teacher, the ability to see the psyche and inner world of students. Then the teacher can predict in advance who is capable of what.

3. Ability to hear and feel: People with this ability love music, have a good sense of melody, read prose and poetry well based on recitation, remember what they hear, especially love to listen to poems and songs.

4. Kinesthetic (skin-muscular) ability: The teacher's ability to coordinate his own movements, directs by feeling the tone of movement, feels time with the pace of movement, can create household comforts for himself, knows how to enjoy the blessings of life.

5. Logical ability: likes philosophical reasoning, numbers, mathematics, solving complex problems, has the ability to understand the results of cause and effect, can distinguish the primary from the secondary in reality;

6. The inner ability of the person: The ability to know, understand and feel oneself perfectly, the inner ability is perfectly developed in a free person, the will is strong, determined, he can express his opinion freely in any situation.

In the analysis of scientific literature, an unclear limit of a number of pedagogical skills is observed:

- the ability to achieve acceptable results, the ability to make corrections to pedagogical logic;
- the ability to see conflicts, and then find a practical solution to it;
- the ability to understand the interlocutor's inner world;
- the ability to actively influence the student body, etc.

These definitions show that the group of pedagogical abilities cannot complement each other. Gnostic, constructive, communicative, organizational, projective-gnostic and reflexive-perceptive; reproductive and creative abilities; such abilities as communicative, constructive, organizational, expressive, perceptive, creative represent "integral characteristics describing the teacher's relative capabilities for activity".

It should be noted that nowadays some researchers completely abandon the term "pedagogical skill" when studying the laws of pedagogical activity or replace it with different terms: for example, advanced pedagogical experience, teacher's creative activity, pedagogical competence, pedagogical technology, etc. However, pedagogic skill is considered to be the most important set of qualities specific to various situations in the teacher's pedagogical activity. Because the analysis of scientific literature dedicated to the study of pedagogical activity from the ninth century to the present shows that what happens in the professional activity of the teacher is determined only by the level of "pedagogical skill" and affects the teacher's ability to increase the effectiveness of pedagogical activity. It is for this reason that "pedagogical skill" is widely explained in our report as a teacher's character, that is, a set of abilities that help to achieve a high level of professional activity.

The importance of the teacher's reflexive ability in the professional pedagogical activity has recently attracted the attention of scientists and is taking place in their scientific research. In fact, reflection (lat. "reflexio" - going back) is "a form of theoretical activity aimed at understanding the characteristics and actions of a fully developed person and the laws of the society in which he lives; it is an activity aimed at self-knowledge and understanding, which reveals the unique hidden features of the spiritual world of a person."¹

Scientifically studying the possibilities of managing the mental development of a person, S. L. Rubinstein connects the existence of a person and his relationship to social existence with reflection:

"Reflection - it stops and cuts off the continuous life process of a person for a moment, and takes a person out of its boundaries in imagination, in this situation, every movement of a person acquires a certain character of philosophical thoughts about life."

In modern pedagogical research, many scientists rely on the classification of reflection proposed by I.N. Semenov. He explains by suggesting the following types of reflection:

¹ Look at: *Философская энциклопедия. – М.: Советская энциклопедия. 1967. – 4-т. 499 б.*

Types of reflection developed by I.N. Semyonov

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| 1. Intellectual reflection: Determines positive problem solving based on thinking. |
| 2. Personal reflection: The conflict (conflicts) of the teacher provides a way out of the pedagogical conflicts without conflicts based on thought research. |
| 3. Communicative reflection: It ensures mutual understanding of partners during communication. |
| 4. Cooperative reflection: An activity related to the coordination of joint regular work activities of team members. |

I.S. Ladenko connects reflection with the need to improve the skills and abilities of a person in his intellectual activity, as well as with his psychological views on the internal and external forms of speech, memory, imagination. He said, "Reflection is the basis for the formation of ideas about the transition from internal imagination to external imagination and vice versa, the internalization of these processes (transition of external factors to internal factors) in the process of thinking... On the basis of reflection, not only psychological knowledge, but also memory, skills and abilities are formed, and methods of practical application are improved" believes.

Pedagogical skill is a systematic characteristic of a teacher, which is manifested, formed and improved in the "live" pedagogical activity of the teacher, helps him to reach a high level of professionalism, and is characterized by the unity of the intellectual, volitional, emotional and physical aspects of the self-management process.

As a result of conducting scientific researches that connect regular live pedagogical activity with real life, the phenomenon of "pedagogical skill" has been enriched with various opinions and considerations. The concept of "pedagogical skill" observed in live pedagogical activity is not imagined as an object consisting of some signs, but is considered an indivisible whole concept, that is, a network of relationships that includes the teacher in a mandatory pedagogical space.

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